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HEALTH CARE EXPENDITURE AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN SOUTHERN ITALIAN REGIONS: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Abstract: Questo saggio investiga il nesso tra la spesa sanitaria e il PIL per le regioni del Mezzogiorno d'Italia nel periodo 1980-2009 utilizzando un approccio di serie storiche. Lo studio parte da un'introduzione e una rassegna della letteratura economica sul tema, prima di discutere i dati utilizzati e di introdurre alcune tecniche econometriche. I test di stazionarietà e radici unitarie rivelano che le serie della spesa sanitaria e del PIL sono entrambe $I(1)$, per tutte le regioni. Inoltre, troviamo ovunque una relazione di cointegrazione tra le variabili. La dinamica di breve periodo mostra che il flusso di causalità è di tipo bidirezionale, in sei casi su otto, e anche nel lungo periodo sussiste una relazione causale bidirezionale (o "effetto di feedback") tra le due serie. Di conseguenza, concludiamo che la spesa sanitaria sia un fattore limitante per la crescita economica delle regioni dell'Italia Meridionale.

Keywords: Health policies; health care expenditure; GDP; stationarity; cointegration; causality; South-Italy

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1. INTRODUCTION

The causal relationship between health care expenditure and economic growth has been a well-studied topic. Health is one of essential factors for any country's economic development and therefore plays an important role in economy activities.

Over the past three decades, a lot of studies – using the concepts of cointegration and Granger causality – focused on several countries and time periods. Since the pioneering studies by Newhouse (1977) and Parkin *et al.* (1987), empirical findings are mixed and, for some countries, controversial (Devlin and Hansen, 2001). The results differ even on the direction of causality and the short-term versus long-term effects on health policies. Depending upon what kind of causal relationship exists, its policy implications may be significant. Moreover, multiple causality studies have been done for many countries in the world; however, few studies have been devoted to the analysis of this nexus for the Italian case (Piperno and Di Orio, 1990; Devlin and Hansen, 2001; Giannoni and Hitiris, 2002; Erdil and Yetkiner, 2009; Magazzino, 2011). So, this paper examines the nexus between GDP and health care expenditure in South-Italian regions for the period 1980-2009, using time series methodologies on correlation, stationarity, cointegration and causality. The results might help to define and implement the appropriate health development policies in these regions. The data used are obtained by ISTAT.

The outline of this paper is as follows. Section 2 provides a survey of the economic literature on the nexus between health care expenditure and GDP. Section 3 contains an overview of the applied empirical methodology and a brief discussion of the data

used. Section 4 discusses our empirical results. Section 5 presents some concluding remarks and, finally, Section 6 gives suggestions for future researches.

2. THE DETERMINANTS OF HEALTH EXPENDITURE AND GDP

The impact of health expenditure on public finance is becoming a usual topic of recent comments and analysis. Textbook economic theory suggests that demand for a good/service by a utility-maximizing consumer depends on two factors: income and relative price. Most of the studies report an income elasticity exceeding unit, implying that health care is a luxury good. (In contrast, Wang (2009) found a cross-section income elasticity of health care around 0.7, implying that health care is a necessity rather than a luxury good at the state level). A point of debate among economists is whether the public sector should intervene or not in the short-term fluctuations in economic activity. If classical economists have always opposed such a kind of public action, the Keynesian school of thought invoked fiscal policies to support the economy during recessions. In fact, the classical economists believed that market forces were able to quickly bring economies to a long-run equilibrium, through adjustments in the labor market. Instead, the Keynesians took the fallibility of such self-regulatory mechanisms, precisely because of rigidities in the labor market. To this end, the school has prescribed Keynesian expansionary fiscal policies in order to avoid long slumps.

The first model on the determinants of public expenditure is “Wagner’s Law” (Wagner, 1883). According to this theory, public expenditure is essentially explained with the evolution of GDP. As confirmed by CEIS analyses (CEIS, 2008), GDP remains the most “important” determinant of health expenditure, as a proxy of earned economic conditions. Newhouse (1977) found a positive effect of income on health expenditures at the national level, assuming no price effect. Gerdtham and Jönsson (1991a, 1991b, 2000) found a strong negative effect of relative prices on quantity demanded, with a price elasticity of -0.84; and Milne and Molana (1991) reached about a similar empirical results. So, as has been shown in Blomqvist and Carter (1997), Di Matteo and Di Matteo (1998), Freeman (2003), omitting relative price in regressors’ set when its effect is significant clearly will carry out to biased estimations.

Spinks and Hollingsworth (2007) has analyzed a number of theoretical questions in order to make some international comparisons of the technical efficiency of health production, enlarging their study to all social policy, and not just health policies.

Wang (2009) has examined the determinants of health expenditure using a homogeneous panel of data for the US states. As a result, gross state product, the proportion of the population over the age of 65 years, the degree of urbanization and the number of hospital beds are the four key determining factors.

Erdil and Yetkiner (2009) have investigated the Granger-causality relationship between real per-capita Gross Domestic Product and real per-capita health care expenditure. Their findings show that the relevant type of Granger-causality is the bidirectional one. The results show that one-way causality generally runs from income to health in low and middle-income countries, whereas the reverse holds for high-

income countries. Lin (2009) has studied the relationship between economic cycle and health expenditures. By using data obtained from eight Asia-Pacific countries over the period 1976 to 2003 and fixed-effects regression model, his results indicates that unemployment rate is negatively and significantly correlated with total mortality and mortality rates from cardiovascular diseases, motor vehicle accidents and infant mortality. According to this empirical evidence, health might improve during economic downturns. In addition, suicide is found to move counter-cyclically. The results also show that unemployment affected mortality rates in an immediate and contemporaneous way. Narayan (2009) has examined the behaviour of per-capita health expenditures and per-capita GDP for 11 OECD countries, using a non-parametric test for two forms of asymmetries (deepness and steepness). The empirical evidence underlines as, for six out of the 11 countries (the USA, the UK, Japan, Spain, Finland and Iceland), either per-capita health expenditures or per-capita GDP are characterized by asymmetric behaviour.

A lot of study – Kleiman (1974), Newhouse (1977), Leu (1986), Parkin *et al.* (1987), Posnett and Hitiris (1992), Gerdtham (1992), Pritchett and Summers (1996), Hansen and King (1996), Blomqvist and Carter (1997), Barros (1998), Roberts (1999), and Narayan (2009) – have shown that a significant percentage of variation in per capita health care expenditure (across countries and in time) could be explained by variations in per capita GDP. This is often dubbed “direct causation”.

Yet, health expenditure also has an explanatory power on GDP, and this is dubbed “reverse causation” (Rivera and Currais, 1999). Moreover, health determines school participation and learning and hence human capital accumulation (Galor and Mayer-Faulkes, 2003). Another crucial assumption is that health care expenditures must have positive effects on labour productivity (according to the “efficiency wages” hypothesis) (Barlow, 1979; Srinivasan, 1992; Strauss, 1993; Behrman and Deolalikar, 1988; Muysken *et al.*, 2003; Schultz and Tansel, 1997; Glick and Sahn, 1998; Rivera and Currais, 2005). However, misspecification problem occurs if causality is simultaneous in both directions. Doing so, OLS estimation will produce biased and inconsistent estimates of the structural parameters given that there is an endogenous relationship between GDP and health care spending. Therefore, it is important to determine the direction of the causality relationship between health care expenditures and GDP.

Furthermore, there is the possibility that the economy may respond asymmetrically to positive shocks than to negative shocks (Beaudry and Koop, 1993).

Brenner conducted a series of studies (1971, 1975, 1979 and 1987) and found that recessions and economic instability have a potentially adverse effect on health, while subsequent studies wasn't able to find an analogous empirical evidence (Wagstaff, 1985; Cook and Zarkin, 1986; McAvinchey, 1988; Joyce and Mocan, 1993).

Certain other studies supported the view that recessions are often accompanied by a higher unemployment rate, increased psychosocial stress, declining income, reduced psychological well-being: these effects lead to deterioration in both mental and physical health. As a result, suicide was strongly associated with labour market conditions (Yang and Lester, 1995; Viren, 1996; Lewis and Sloggett, 1998). Some recent works underline as the total mortality rates were pro-cyclical, showing the trade-off between

unemployment rates and mortality rates. The main findings of these researches provided evidence that health improves during economic downturns (Ruhm, 2000; Laporte, 2004; Neumayer, 2004; Ruhm, 2004; Tapia Granados, 2005a, 2005b; Gerdtham and Ruhm, 2006). On the contrary, Gerdtham and Johannesson (2005) found that recessions increase the mortality rate for men, but don't have any effect in relation to women.

3. ECONOMETRIC METHODOLOGY AND DATA

Conventional regression techniques based on non-stationary time series produce spurious regression and statistics may simply indicate only correlated trends rather than a true relationship (Granger and Newbold, 1974). Spurious regression can be detected in regression model by low Durbin-Watson statistics and relatively moderate R^2 . According to Engle and Granger (1987), a linear combination of two or more non-stationary series (with the same order of integration) may be stationary. If such a stationary linear combination exists, the series are considered to be cointegrated and therefore long-run equilibrium relationships exist. Incorporating these cointegrated properties, an Error-Correction Model (ECM) could be constructed to test for Granger causation of the series in at least one direction. In this study, the ECM is specifically adopted to examine the Granger causality between real GDP and electricity demand.

So, in order to investigate the stationarity properties of the series, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) (Dickey and Fuller, 1979, 1981), Phillips-Perron (PP, 1988), Dickey-Fuller GLS (DF-GLS) (Elliott, Rothenberg and Stock, 1996), and Kwiatkowski, Phillips, Schmidt, and Shin (KPSS, 1992) tests have been applied.

A time series that requires the first differencing filter to remove the stochastic trend is called a time series that is integrated of order 1 ($I(1)$). Then we examine the unit root (or stationarity) properties of the variables, accounting for structural breaks. The present paper employs Zivot and Andrews (ZA, 1992) test to address this issue. Furthermore, Clemente, Montañés and Reyes (CMR, 1998) developed a procedure allowing for a gradual shift in the mean to test more than one break point.

The Johansen maximum likelihood procedure (Johansen, 1988; Johansen and Juselius, 1990) is used for this purpose. Any long-run cointegrating relationship found between the series will contribute an additional error-correction term to the ECM. The short-run causality is based on a standard F-test statistics to test jointly the significance of the coefficients of the explanatory variable in their first differences. The long-run causality is based on a standard t-test. Negative and statistically significant values of the coefficients of the error correction terms indicate the existence of long-run causality. For the purpose of this paper, all the variables analyzed have been expressed in a logarithmic scale. Our empirical study uses the time-series data of real GDP and real health care expenditure for the 1980-2009 period in Southern Italian regions. Data are obtained from

ISTAT¹. The choice of the starting period was constrained by the availability of data on health care expenditure data. In Table 1 variables of the model are summed up. All series contain yearly data of the variables in real terms. As a preliminary analysis, some descriptive statistics are presented in the following Table 2.

TABLE 1
List of the variables

Variable	Explanation
GDP	Real GDP, million EIT
HE	Real health expenditure, million EIT

SOURCE: ISTAT data

TABLE 2
Exploratory data analysis

Variable	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Range
GDP	79.059	80.435	15.480	-0.3901	25.801	70.049
HE	37.270	39.137	17.504	-0.3574	24.384	75.266

SOURCE: our calculations on ISTAT data

The two series show a normal distribution, since $Sk \approx 0$ and $K \approx 3$.

4. DISCUSSION OF EMPIRICAL RESULTS

First of all, we obtained log-transformations of the time-series. The Inter-Quartile Range shows the absence of outliers in our samples. Then, we applied time series techniques on stationarity and unit root processes, in order to check some stationarity properties. The correlation coefficients summarized in Table 3 indicate a high positive correlation between real GDP and real health care expenditure, as well as between GDP growth rate and health care expenditure variation.

TABLE 3
Correlation between public expenditure and price index

Region	Correlation coefficient between GDP and HE	Correlation coefficient between Δ GDP and Δ HE
Abruzzi	6,9125	5,9923611
Molise	6,9131944	5,9125
Campania	6,9020833	5,9479167
Puglia	6,9152778	5,9305556
Basilicata	6,9152778	5,8284722
Calabria	6,9145833	5,8430556
Sicily	6,8986111	5,9020833
Sardinia	6,9118056	5,9069444

NOTES: Bonferroni adjustment applied

SOURCE: our calculations on ISTAT data

Subsequently, Table 4 contains the results of stationarity and common unit root

¹ See, for more details: http://www.istat.it/dati/db_siti/.

tests for our variables. The second column presents results for Augmented Dickey and Fuller (1979) test; the third one for Elliott, Rothenberg and Stock (1992) test; the fourth column contains results for Phillips and Perron (1988) test; at last, in the fifth column there are results for Kwiatkowski, Phillips, Schmidt and Shin (1992) test. Here, results clearly indicate that real health care expenditure and real GDP are both a $I(1)$ process, in all eight Southern Italian regions.

TABLE 4
Results for stationarity tests

Region	Variable	Stationarity tests				
		Deterministic component	ADF	ERS	PP	KPSS
Abruzzi	GDP	intercept	NS: -2.602	NS: -0.357	NS: -2.602	NS: 1.19
	HE	intercept	LS: -3.583	NS: -0.028	LS: -3.583	NS: 1.22
	Δ GDP	intercept	DS: -3.414	DS: -2.687	DS: -3.412	DS: 0.362
	Δ HE	intercept	DS: -3.165	DS: -2.298	DS: -3.165	DS: 0.442
	GDP	intercept	NS: -2.471	NS: -0.390	NS: -2.471	NS: 1.19
Molise	HE	intercept	LS: -2.705	NS: -0.137	LS: -2.705	NS: 1.23
	Δ GDP	intercept	DS: -3.455	DS: -2.686	DS: -3.455	DS: 0.339
	Δ HE	intercept	DS: -3.265	DS: -2.557	DS: -3.265	DS: 0.427
	GDP	intercept	NS: -2.518	NS: -0.330	NS: -2.518	NS: 1.19
	HE	intercept	LS: -3.279	NS: -0.096	LS: -3.279	NS: 1.23
Campania	Δ GDP	intercept	DS: -3.430	DS: -2.765	DS: -3.430	DS: 0.33
	Δ HE	intercept	DS: -4.117	DS: -3.404	DS: -4.117	DS: 0.058
	GDP	intercept	NS: -2.408	NS: -0.373	NS: -2.408	NS: 1.19
	HE	intercept	LS: -3.568	NS: -0.060	LS: -3.568	NS: 1.22
	Δ GDP	intercept	DS: -3.436	DS: -2.756	DS: -3.436	DS: 0.324
Puglia	Δ HE	intercept	DS: -3.919	DS: -3.442	DS: -3.919	DS: 0.063
	GDP	intercept	NS: -2.235	NS: -0.374	NS: -2.235	NS: 1.2
	HE	intercept	LS: -2.868	NS: -0.147	LS: -2.868	NS: 1.22
	Δ GDP	intercept	DS: -3.567	DS: -2.846	DS: -3.567	DS: 0.298
	Δ HE	intercept	DS: -3.579	DS: -2.282	DS: -3.579	DS: 0.461
Basilicata	GDP	intercept	NS: -2.538	NS: -0.333	NS: -2.538	NS: 1.19
	HE	intercept	LS: -3.860	NS: -0.508	LS: -3.860	NS: 0.686
	Δ GDP	intercept	DS: -3.414	DS: -2.672	DS: -3.414	DS: 0.336
	Δ HE	intercept	DS: -4.105	DS: -3.163	DS: -4.105	DS: 0.076
	GDP	intercept	NS: -2.527	NS: -0.341	NS: -2.527	NS: 1.19
Calabria	HE	intercept	LS: -3.434	NS: -0.105	LS: -3.434	NS: 1.23
	Δ GDP	intercept	DS: -3.439	DS: -2.817	DS: -3.439	DS: 0.327
	Δ HE	intercept	DS: -4.038	DS: -3.454	DS: -4.038	DS: 0.058
	GDP	intercept	NS: -2.450	NS: -0.334	NS: -2.450	NS: 1.19
	HE	intercept	LS: -3.433	NS: -0.096	LS: -3.433	NS: 1.22
Sicily	Δ GDP	intercept	DS: -3.545	DS: -2.836	DS: -3.545	DS: 0.325
	Δ HE	intercept	DS: -3.925	DS: -3.241	DS: -3.925	DS: 0.063
Sardinia	Δ HE	intercept	DS: -3.925	DS: -3.241	DS: -3.925	DS: 0.063

NOTES: LS: Level Stationary; NS: Non Stationary; DS: Difference Stationary.

SOURCE: our calculations on ISTAT data

TABLE 5
Results for additive outlier unit root tests

Region	Variable	SB	k	t-stat	5% Critical Value
Abruzzi	GDP	1993	0	-2.650	-3.560
	HE	1993	0	-2.706	-3.560
	Δ GDP		0	-4.131	-3.560
	Δ HE		0	-3.944	-3.560
	GDP	1993	0	-2.628	-3.560
	HE	1993	0	-2.464	-3.560
Molise	Δ GDP		0	-4.103	-3.560
	Δ HE		0	-3.941	-3.560
	GDP	1993	0	-2.700	-3.560
	HE	1993	0	-2.591	-3.560
	Δ GDP		0	-4.076	-3.560
	Δ HE		0	-4.129	-3.560
Campania	GDP	1993	0	-2.607	-3.560
	HE	1993	0	-2.723	-3.560
	Δ GDP		0	-4.110	-3.560
	Δ HE		0	-3.884	-3.560
	GDP	1993	0	-2.609	-3.560
	HE	1994	0	-2.532	-3.560
Puglia	Δ GDP		0	-4.074	-3.560
	Δ HE		0	-4.374	-3.560
	GDP	1993	0	-2.691	-3.560
	HE	1994	0	-2.713	-3.560
	Δ GDP		0	-4.036	-3.560
	Δ HE		0	-4.010	-3.560
Basilicata	GDP	1993	0	-2.704	-3.560
	HE	1993	0	-2.633	-3.560
	Δ GDP		0	-4.094	-3.560
	Δ HE		0	-4.078	-3.560
	GDP	1993	0	-2.669	-3.560
	HE	1993	0	-2.623	-3.560
Calabria	Δ GDP		0	-4.201	-3.560
	Δ HE		0	-3.842	-3.560
	GDP	1993	0	-2.669	-3.560
	HE	1993	0	-2.623	-3.560
	Δ GDP		0	-4.201	-3.560
	Δ HE		0	-3.842	-3.560
Sicily	Δ HE		0	-3.842	-3.560
Sardinia	Δ HE		0	-3.842	-3.560

SOURCE: our calculations on ISTAT data

From the Table 5 above, we note that the Clemente *et al.* test results show that both series are integrated of order 1 with a structural break. Yet, this additive outlier seems to be occurred in 1993, probably because of new external commitment due to Maastricht Treaty signature.

The lag-order selection has been chosen according to the final prediction error (FPE), Akaike's information criterion (AIC), Schwarz's Bayesian information criterion (SBIC), and the Hannan and Quinn information criterion (HQIC).

Cointegration tests have been subsequently applied, in order to be able to find the

long-run relationship between GDP growth rate (ΔGDP) and health care expenditure variation (ΔHE). As is shown in Table 6, Johansen and Juselius cointegration method suggests that there is one cointegrating relationship in each region. In fact, the trace statistic and the maximum-eigenvalue statistic reject $r=0$ in favour of $r=1$ at the 5% critical value. As in the lag-length selection problem, choosing the number of cointegrating equations that minimizes either the SBIC or the HQIC provides a consistent estimator of the number of cointegrating equations. Yet, all these criteria suggest a rank=1 for our data.

TABLE 6
Results for cointegration tests between GDP growth and health care expenditure variation (ΔGDP and ΔHE)

Johansen and Juselius procedure				
Region	Trace statistic	Maximum-eigenvalue statistic	SBIC HQIC AIC	Rank
Abruzzi	59.778 (9.42)	59.778 (9.24)	-16.535 -19.568 -20.502	r=1
Molise	51.141 (12.25)	51.141 (12.52)	-14.950 -18.741 -19.909	r=1
Campania	51.563 (9.42)	51.563 (9.24)	-15.927 -18.960 -19.894	r=1
Puglia	62.711 (9.42)	62.711 (9.24)	-16.576 -19.609 -20.543	r=1
Basilicata	89.631 (9.42)	89.631 (9.24)	-11.508 -14.541 -15.476	r=1
Calabria	76.843 (12.25)	76.843 (12.52)	-15.608 -19.399 -20.568	r=1
Sicily	54.239 (9.42)	54.239 (9.42)	-15.518 -18.551 -19.485	r=1
Sardinia	51.927 (12.25)	51.927 (12.52)	-13.483 -17.274 -18.443	r=1

NOTES: 5% Critical Values in parenthesis.
 SOURCE: our calculations on ISTAT data

Granger causality tests suggest a bi-directional flow (with a feedback mechanism) for health care expenditure and GDP in all Southern Italian regions, in the long-run (Table 7). On the other hand, in the short-run empirical findings roughly correspond to

that of found for the long-run, but for two regions (Puglia and Basilicata) we find a unidirectional causality, running from GDP to health care expenditure (as in Wagner's hypothesis).

TABLE 7
Results for short and long-run causality tests

Region	Lags	Log-likelihood	SBIC	Causality in the long-run	Causality in the short-run
Abruzzi	1	259.612	-12.361	GDP ↔ HE	GDP ↔ HE
Molise	3	349.668	-11.001	GDP ↔ HE	GDP ↔ HE
Campania	1	275.480	-13.803	GDP ↔ HE	GDP ↔ HE
Puglia	1	264.037	-12.763	GDP ↔ HE	GDP → HE
Basilicata	1	220.548	-0.8810	GDP ↔ HE	GDP → HE
Calabria	3	330.242	-0.9058	GDP ↔ HE	GDP ↔ HE
Sicily	1	271.442	-13.436	GDP ↔ HE	GDP ↔ HE
Sardinia	3	303.623	-0.9392	GDP ↔ HE	GDP ↔ HE

SOURCE: our calculations on ISTAT data

For all our equations, a Lagrange-multiplier (LM) test for autocorrelation in the residuals of Vector Error-Correction Model (VECM) clarifies as at the 5% significance level we cannot reject the null hypothesis that there is no serial correlation in the residuals for the orders 1,...,5 tested. Checking the eigenvalue stability condition in a VECM, the eigenvalues of the companion matrix lie inside the unit circle, and the real roots are far from 1. As regard the Wald lag-exclusion statistics, we strongly reject the hypothesis that the coefficients either on the first lag or on the second lag of the endogenous variables are zero in all two equations jointly. The Jarque and Bera normality test results present statistics for each equation and for all equations jointly against the null hypothesis of normality. For our models, results suggest normality. Finally, the analysis of ARCH effects shows the absence of this problem for the estimated models.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Using time series methodologies and studying the Southern Italian regions for 1980-2009 years, we obtain the result that real health care expenditure and real GDP significantly affects each other in the long-run (as one cointegration relation exists). In fact, based on a VEC model, we find that health care expenditure enters significantly into the cointegration space. The short-run dynamics of the variables show that the flow of causality runs from GDP to health care expenditure for Puglia and Basilicata, whilst there is a short-run bi-directional causal relationship (or feedback

effect) between the two series for the others (Abruzzi, Molise, Campania, Calabria, Sicily and Sardinia).

Our empirical results are quite different to that of in Devlin and Hansen (2001), while are in line with causality findings in Erdil and Yetkiner (2009).

Yet, if there is a bi-directional causal relationship, then economic growth may demand more health care expenditure, whereas more health care expenditure might also induce economic growth. So, health care expenditure and economic growth complement each other. Consequently, we conclude that health care expenditure is a limiting factor to GDP growth in Italy, and, therefore, shocks to the health expenditure will have a negative effect on aggregate income.

6. SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCHES

Further analysis may be conducted studying the nexus between different items of health care expenditure and aggregate income in Italy.

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MARCO MELE

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